

Mémoire pour l'obtention du Diplôme d'Études Spécialisées Complémentaires de Psychiatrie de l'Enfant et de l'Adolescent

Présenté et soutenu

Le 29 mars 2018 par

François A. M. Jean

Né le 11 avril 1987 à Lannemezan

Anxiété, Dépression et Regard dans le Trouble du Spectre de l'Autisme : Étude en Oculométrie

Directeur de mémoire

Madame le Docteur *Anouck Amestoy*, Centre Ressources Autisme Aquitaine

Jury

Monsieur le Professeur *Laurent Schmitt*, Université de Toulouse

Monsieur le Professeur *Manuel Bouvard*, Université de Bordeaux

Monsieur le Professeur *Jean-Philippe Raynaud*, Université de Toulouse

Madame le Professeur *Hélène Verdoux*, Université de Bordeaux

Monsieur le Professeur *Jean-Pierre Clément*, Université de Limoges

Monsieur le Professeur *Marc Auriacombe*, Université de Bordeaux

Monsieur le Professeur *Philippe Birmes*, Université de Toulouse

Monsieur le Professeur *Bruno Aouizerate*, Université de Bordeaux

Monsieur le Professeur *Louis Jehel*, CHU de Fort-de-France

Monsieur le Professeur *Christophe Arbus*, Université de Toulouse

Madame le Professeur *Marie Tournier*, Université de Bordeaux

Monsieur le Professeur *Philippe Nubukpo*, Université de Limoges

Monsieur le Professeur *Cédric Galéra*, Université de Bordeaux

Mémoire pour l'obtention du Diplôme d'Études Spécialisées Complémentaires de Psychiatrie de l'Enfant et de l'Adolescent

Présenté et soutenu

Le 29 mars 2018 par

François A. M. Jean

Né le 11 avril 1987 à Lannemezan

Anxiété, Dépression et Regard dans le Trouble du Spectre de l'Autisme : Étude en Oculométrie

Directeur de mémoire

Madame le Docteur *Anouck Amestoy*, Centre Ressources Autisme Aquitaine

Jury

Monsieur le Professeur *Laurent Schmitt*, Université de Toulouse

Monsieur le Professeur *Manuel Bouvard*, Université de Bordeaux

Monsieur le Professeur *Jean-Philippe Raynaud*, Université de Toulouse

Madame le Professeur *Hélène Verdoux*, Université de Bordeaux

Monsieur le Professeur *Jean-Pierre Clément*, Université de Limoges

Monsieur le Professeur *Marc Auriacombe*, Université de Bordeaux

Monsieur le Professeur *Philippe Birmes*, Université de Toulouse

Monsieur le Professeur *Bruno Aouizerate*, Université de Bordeaux

Monsieur le Professeur *Louis Jehel*, CHU de Fort-de-France

Monsieur le Professeur *Christophe Arbus*, Université de Toulouse

Madame le Professeur *Marie Tournier*, Université de Bordeaux

Monsieur le Professeur *Philippe Nubukpo*, Université de Limoges

Monsieur le Professeur *Cédric Galéra*, Université de Bordeaux

Coordonnées du jury

Psychiatrie Adulte	Pédo-Psychiatrie
BORDEAUX	
<p>Professeur Bruno AOUIZERATE Centre de référence régional des pathologies anxieuses et de la dépression Pôle de Psychiatrie générale et universitaire Centre Hospitalier Charles Perrens 121 rue de la Béchade - CS 81285 33076 BORDEAUX Cedex Tél. : 05.56.56.17.98 Fax : 05.56.56.17.22 e-mail : bruno.aouizerate@u-bordeaux2.fr</p>	<p>Professeur Manuel BOUVARD Pôle Universitaire de Psychiatrie de l'Enfant et de l'Adolescent Centre Hospitalier Charles Perrens 121 rue de la Béchade - CS 81285 33076 BORDEAUX Cedex Tél. : 05.56.56.17.19 Fax : 05.56.56.17.15 e-mail : mbouvard@ch-perrens.fr , slafenetre@ch-perrens.fr</p>
<p>Professeur Marc AURIACOMBE Pôle Addictologie Centre Hospitalier Charles Perrens 121 rue de la Béchade - CS 81285 33076 BORDEAUX Cedex Tél. : 05.56.56.17.38 Fax : 05.56.56.17.27 e-mail : marc.auriacombe@u-bordeaux.fr</p>	<p>Professeur Cédric GALERA Pôle Universitaire de Psychiatrie de l'Enfant et de l'Adolescent Centre Hospitalier Charles Perrens 121 rue de la Béchade - CS 81285 33076 BORDEAUX Cedex Tél. : 05.56.56.17.19 Fax : 05.56.56.17.15 e-mail : cgalera@ch-perrens.fr</p>
<p>Professeur Hélène VERDOUX Pôle Universitaire de Psychiatrie Adulte Hôpital Charles Perrens 121 rue de la Béchade - CS 81285 33076 BORDEAUX Cedex Tél. : 05.56.56.17.32 Fax : 05.56.56.35.46 e-mail : hverdoux@ch-perrens.fr</p>	
<p>Professeur Marie TOURNIER Pôle Universitaire de Psychiatrie Adulte Hôpital Charles Perrens 121 rue de la Béchade - CS 81285 33076 BORDEAUX Cedex Tél. : 05.56.56.17.71 ou 17 32 Fax : 05.56.56.35.46 e-mail : mtournier@ch-perrens.fr</p>	
ANTILLES GUYANE	
<p>Professeur Louis JEHEL CHU de Fort-de-France - Service de Psychologie Médicale et de Psychiatrie - Service 1C - B. P. 632 97261 FORT-de-FRANCE Cedex MARTINIQUE Tél. : 05 96 55 22 11 e-mail : louis.jehel@chu-fortdefrance.fr venise.opet@univ.ag.fr</p>	

LIMOGES	
<p>Professeur Jean-Pierre CLEMENT Fédération Hospitalo-Universitaire de Psychiatrie de l'Adulte et du Sujet Agé Centre Hospitalier ESQUIROL 15 rue du Docteur Marcland 87025 LIMOGES Cedex Tél. : 05.55.43.11.92 Fax : 05.55.43.11.95 e-mail : pc4@ch-esquirol-limoges.fr</p>	
<p>Professeur Philippe NUBUKPO Pôle Universitaire d'Addictologie Centre Hospitalier ESQUIROL 15 rue du Docteur Marcland 87025 LIMOGES Cedex Tél. : 05.55.43.13.21 Fax : 05.55.43.12.46 e-mail : philippe.nubukpo@ch-esquirol-limoges.fr philippe.nubukpo@9online.fr</p>	
TOULOUSE	
<p>Professeur Laurent SCHMITT Service Universitaire de Psychiatrie et Psychologie Médicale Hôpital de Psychiatrie 330 avenue de Grande Bretagne TSA 70034 31059 TOULOUSE Cedex 9 Tél. : 05.34.55.75.02 Fax : 05.34.55.75.15 e-mail : schmitt.l@chu-toulouse.fr schmitt.sec@chu-toulouse.fr</p>	<p>Professeur Jean-Philippe RAYNAUD Service Universitaire de Psychiatrie de l'Enfant et de l'Adolescent (S.U.P.E.A.) Hôpital La Grave TSA 60033 31059 TOULOUSE Cedex 9 Tél. : 05.61.77.78.74 Fax : 05.61.77.79.02 e-mail : raynaud.jp@chu-toulouse.fr payeur.g@chu-toulouse.fr</p>
<p>Professeur Philippe BIRMES Service de Psychiatrie, psychothérapies et art-thérapie Hôpital de Psychiatrie 330 avenue de Grande Bretagne TSA 70034 31059 TOULOUSE Cedex 9 Tél. : 05.34.55.75.05 Fax : 05.34.55.75.16 e-mail : birmes.p@chu-toulouse.fr birmes.sec@chu-toulouse.fr</p>	
<p>Professeur Christophe ARBUS Service Universitaire de Psychiatrie et Psychologie Médicale Hôpital de Psychiatrie 330 avenue de Grande Bretagne TSA 70034 31059 TOULOUSE Cedex 9 Tél. : 05.34.55.75.04 Fax : 05.34.55.75.15 e-mail : arbus.c@chu-toulouse.fr arbus.sec@chu-toulouse.fr</p>	

Table des Matières

Coordonnées du jury.....	1
Table des Matières.....	3
Abréviations.....	4
Parcours.....	5
1.Introduction générale.....	6
2.Oculométrie.....	8
3.Anxiety, Depression and Gaze in Autism Spectrum Disorder : an Eye-tracking Study.....	10
Collaborations et Financement.....	11
Conflits d'intérêt.....	11
Résumé.....	12
Mots clefs.....	12
Abstract.....	13
Key words.....	13
Introduction.....	14
Methods.....	16
Results.....	20
Discussion.....	28
References.....	30
4.Conclusion générale.....	36
Références.....	37
Index des Tableaux.....	41
Index des Figures.....	41

Abréviations

- %: percentages
- AOI: Area Of Interest
- ASD: Autism Spectrum Disorder
- beta: regression slope
- DSM-5: Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders – 5
- HARS: Hamilton Anxiety Rating Scale
- HDRS: Hamilton Depression Rating Scale
- INSERM: Institut National de la Santé Et de la Recherche Médicale
- LSAS: Liebowitz Social Anxiety Scale
- m: mean
- ms: milliseconds
- n: count
- p: p value
- sd: standard deviation
- SRS: Social Responsiveness Scale
- rho: coefficient of correlation of Spearman
- r: coefficient of correlation of Pearson
- R²: coefficient of determination
- RBS-R: Repetitive Behavior Scale – Revised
- TSA: Trouble du Spectre de l'Autisme

Parcours

2012 – 2017 **Internat de Psychiatrie à Bordeaux**

- Novembre 2012 - Avril 2013 : **Unité Fermée Adulte**, Régis, Dr Bernard Antoniol, PH - Expert judiciaire, Hôpital Charles Perrens à Bordeaux
- Mai 2013 - Octobre 2013 : **Unité Ouverte Adulte**, Carreire 3, Pr Marie Tournier, PU-PH, Hôpital Charles Perrens à Bordeaux
- Novembre 2013 - Avril 2014 : Stage hors filière, **Neuropédiatrie**, 6e C, Dr Jean-Michel Pedespan, PH, Hôpital des enfants, Groupe hospitalier Pellegrin, CHU de Bordeaux
- Mai 2014 - Octobre 2014 : **Centre Médico-Psychologique pour Enfants et Adolescents et Centre Ressources Autisme Aquitaine**, Pr Manuel Bouvard, PU-PH, Hôpital Charles Perrens à Bordeaux
- Novembre 2014 - Avril 2015 : **Service d'Addictologie, unité de suivi ambulatoire**, Pr Marc Auriacombe, PU-PH, Hôpital Charles Perrens à Bordeaux
- Novembre 2015 - Avril 2016 : **Urgences psychiatriques**, Service d'Évaluation de Crise et d'Orientation Psychiatrique, Dr Charles-Henry Martin, PH - Référent CUMP Sud-Ouest, Hôpital Charles Perrens à Bordeaux
- Mai 2016 – Octobre 2016 : **Liaison-Urgences pédopsychiatriques à l'hôpital des enfants de Bordeaux et Hôpital De Jour pour enfants à Caychac**, Pr Manuel Bouvard, PU-PH, CHU de Bordeaux et Hôpital Charles Perrens à Bordeaux
- Novembre 2016 – Avril 2017 : **Unité des troubles du comportement alimentaire pour adolescents**, Dr Xavier Pommereau, PH, CHU de Bordeaux

2014 – 2016 **Master 2 Recherche** Biologie Santé Environnement, spécialité Cognition Naturelle et Artificielle, à l'École Pratique des Hautes Études (EPHE) à Paris, Responsable : Pr Thierry Dupressoir

2015 – 2016 Inscription en 1^{er} année du **DESC de Psychiatrie de l'enfant et l'adolescent**

2017 **Doctorat en médecine et DES de Psychiatrie** « Perturbations émotionnelles dans le trouble du spectre de l'autisme »

2017 – 2019 **Chef de Clinique Assistant** dans le Pôle Universitaire de Psychiatrie de l'Enfant et de l'Adolescent du Pr Manuel Bouvard à l'hôpital Charles Perrens à Bordeaux

- Mai 2017 – Avril 2018 : **Liaison-Urgences pédopsychiatriques à l'hôpital des enfants de Bordeaux et Centre de Référence Déficits de l'Attention et Hyperactivité**, Pr Manuel Bouvard, PU-PH, CHU de Bordeaux et Hôpital Charles Perrens à Bordeaux

2017 – 2018 Inscription en 2^e année du **DESC de Psychiatrie de l'enfant et l'adolescent**

1. Introduction générale

Le trouble du spectre de l'autisme (TSA) est un trouble neurodéveloppemental caractérisé par la présence de deux dimensions cliniques principales (American Psychiatric Association, 2013). La première dimension est l'altération des interactions sociales et de la communication sociale. La seconde dimension intègre les intérêts restreints et les comportements répétitifs. Il existe en sus de ces deux dimensions des particularités sensorielles et des troubles du comportement dans le TSA.

Avec une prévalence autour de 1,3 % que cela soit chez l'enfant (Christensen et al., 2016) ou l'adulte (The NHS Information Centre, Community and Mental Health Team et al., 2012) l'autisme est une pathologie concernant a priori 871 000 personnes en France. C'est une préoccupation de santé publique importante qui fait l'objet de plans dédiés. L'année 2018 est l'année du lancement du 4^e plan qui constitue un engagement du Président de la République et dont le caractère prioritaire a été rappelé dans le cadre de la communication en conseil des ministres (« 4^e plan autisme - L'autisme - Secrétariat d'État auprès du Premier ministre chargé des Personnes handicapées », s. d.). Madame le Professeur Dominique Le Guludec, présidente de la haute autorité de santé, dans une tribune récente accompagnant la sortie des recommandations pour la prise en charge du TSA à l'âge adulte et la mise à jour de la prise en charge dans l'enfance évoque les difficultés rencontrées pour les sujets ayant un TSA et leur familles (« Haute Autorité de Santé - "Autisme : poursuivons nos efforts" - Tribune de la présidente de la HAS », s. d.). Elle décrit des parcours bien « souvent chaotique[s], fait d'errances et de ruptures » dans un contexte d'une offre de soins non organisée. L'absence de prise en charge du TSA à l'âge adulte est d'autant plus à regretter lorsqu'elle est comparée avec l'offre pour d'autres pathologies mentales graves. Bien que la prévalence de la schizophrénie, 0,4 % (Bhugra, 2005), soit plus faible que celle du TSA, nous n'avons personnellement jamais eu affaire à un centre de consultation refusant de prendre en charge ce trouble.

Nonobstant les difficultés d'accès aux soins, il est primordial dans le suivi des personnes avec un TSA de se préoccuper des comorbidités psychiatriques pouvant survenir chez elle. La toute récente recommandation de la haute autorité de santé (validée en décembre 2017 et publiée en février 2018) concernant la prise en charge des sujets ayant un TSA à l'âge adulte évoque ce sujet. Il est recommandé d'« être attentif à rechercher des comorbidités psychiatriques » (Haute Autorité de Santé & Agence Nationale de l'évaluation et de la qualité des établissements et services sociaux et médico-sociaux, 2017). La question des comorbidités psychiatriques est primordiale du fait de leur grande prévalence. Environ 7 sujets sur 10, enfants et adultes ayant un TSA, présentent une comorbidité psychiatrique (Houghton, Ong, & Bolognani, 2017; Simonoff et al., 2008). Les

principales comorbidités sont le trouble déficit de l'attention / hyperactivité, le trouble oppositionnel avec provocation, les tics, les troubles anxieux, les troubles dépressifs et l'énurésie. Les troubles de l'humeur et anxieux sont particulièrement retrouvés avec des taux allant respectivement jusqu'à 50 % pour les troubles anxieux et 70 % pour la dépression (Joshi et al., 2010, 2013; Luggnégård, Hallerbäck, & Gillberg, 2011; Muris, Steerneman, Merckelbach, Holdrinet, & Meesters, 1998; Nah, Brewer, Young, & Flower, 2017). Ces comorbidités ont un grand retentissement. Elles sont une cause de traitement médicamenteux (Kirino, 2014). Par ailleurs, la dépression est particulièrement liée au processus suicidaire (Cassidy et al., 2014). La détection d'une comorbidité psychiatrique peut être difficile pour le clinicien du fait du trouble de la communication du TSA. De la même manière, l'objectivation d'un TSA non connu chez un sujet adulte peut être particulièrement ardue devant un motif de consultation du type trouble de l'humeur, trouble anxieux ou tentative de suicide.

Dans le cadre de la fondation FondaMental, une cohorte de patients ayant un TSA avec un haut fonctionnement a été constituée. Cette cohorte est issue de la coopération de trois centres experts Asperger à Bordeaux, Créteil et Paris. Il s'agit de l'étude InFoR autism. Cette cohorte comportait des évaluations cliniques et para-cliniques comprenant notamment une batterie de tâches en oculométrie. Dans le cadre de l'étude InFoR autism, nous avons réalisé un travail concernant les comorbidités psychiatriques dans le TSA et le regard évalué en oculométrie. Ce travail est présenté sous le format d'un article scientifique original après une brève présentation de l'oculométrie.

2. Oculométrie

L'oculométrie, plus connue sous le nom anglais d'eye-tracking, est une technique de mesure de la fixation du regard et du mouvement des yeux. Elle permet de décrire le comportement visuel. Le champ d'application de cette technique est vaste et inclus par exemple l'étude de la lecture (Rayner, 1998), le marketing (Wedel & Pieters, 2008) et la relation humain-ordinateur (Hyönä, Radach, & Deubel, 2003).

L'oculométrie a été utilisée dès 1908 dans l'étude des maladies mentales par Diefendorf et Dodge (Diefendorf & Dodge, 1908). L'altération des saccades et des mouvements de poursuite oculaires est retrouvée dans des troubles comme la schizophrénie, la dépression, les troubles anxieux et le trouble affectif bipolaire chez l'adulte et chez l'enfant (Bittencourt et al., 2013; Rommelse, Van der Stigchel, & Sergeant, 2008). Des altérations ont aussi été retrouvées pour les sujets avec un TSA (Chita-Tegmark, 2016; Dawson, Webb, & McPartland, 2005; Rutherford, Clements, & Sekuler, 2007).

Le comportement visuel a été décrit par Louis Emile Javal, ophtalmologue français et directeur du laboratoire d'ophtalmologie de la Sorbonne, en 1879 (Huey, 1908), comme étant composé d'arrêts courts, appelés fixations, et de mouvements rapides, appelés saccades. L'ensemble des fixations et des saccades reportées sur une image caractérise le trajet exploratoire (scanpath en anglais) sur l'image.

La mesure du mouvement des yeux peut se faire de trois manières différentes. La première technique consiste à mesurer les mouvements à l'aide d'un lien physique avec l'œil. Il s'agit souvent de lentilles associées à un jeu d'aimants ou de miroirs. L'électro-oculographie (ou EOG) mesure les modifications du potentiel électrique de chaque œil induites par leurs mouvements. Cette technique utilise des électrodes placées tout autour des yeux. Enfin il existe la vidéo-oculo-graphie (ou VOG). Une caméra enregistre les mouvements de l'œil et notamment du centre de la pupille. Cette technique peut être combinée avec la projection sur la cornée d'une lumière infra-rouge. Ce procédé permet de calculer l'angulation de mouvement et de déterminer la zone regardée sur l'écran ainsi que le temps passé sur la zone. Le vecteur entre le centre de la pupille et la zone de réflexion donne l'angulation du mouvement dans l'axe haut-bas et dans l'axe droite-gauche. Ce vecteur est visible sur la figure a. A partir du point initial, avec l'angulation du mouvement et la distance œil-cran, il est possible de calculer sur quelle zone de l'image le centre de la pupille est dirigé. Cette technique permet ainsi d'étudier le trajet exploratoire. Les dispositifs actuels d'eye-tracking peuvent être fixes ou mobiles sous la forme de lunettes.

Figure a : Représentation de l'obtention du vecteur entre le centre de la pupille et la réflexion cornéenne permettant de calculer la rotation de l'œil.

Source : https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Eye_tracking#/media/File:Visible_light_eye-tracking_algorithm.jpg

Dans les protocoles de recherche, des mesures en eye-tracking sont intégrées dans des tâches spécifiques. Ces protocoles sont très variables. En général le sujet doit observer une image, une série d'images ou une vidéo. Ces supports visuels peuvent correspondre à des thèmes très variés. La consigne associée à la tâche peut être juste d'observer (éventuellement une région spécifique) soit d'indiquer si une chose est présente ou non. Par exemple, des images de visages peuvent être projetées et le sujet doit déterminer si le visage est celui d'un homme ou celui d'une femme.

Une fois la tâche effectuée, un traitement numérique est appliqué sur les données enregistrées pour déterminer les fixations et les saccades. Un autre traitement peut être appliqué pour découper l'image en zones d'intérêts et calculer le temps passé sur chaque zone ou le nombre de fois où le sujet a fixé la zone. Par exemple, pour une image contenant un visage, il est possible de définir des zones comme le nez, les yeux, la bouche, la face ou la zone hors visage.

La technique de l'oculométrie est un outil précieux pour caractériser le comportement visuel dans différentes conditions.

3. Anxiety, Depression and Gaze in Autism Spectrum Disorder : an Eye-tracking Study

F.A.M. Jean^{1,2}, J. Bucchioni³, E. Guillaud³, J-R. Cazalets³, A. Jouni², M.P. Bouvard^{1,2,3,4}, A. Beggiato^{5,6}, I. Scheid^{4,7}, A. Gaman^{4,7}, F. Bolognani⁸, M. Caralp⁸, S. Gueguen⁸, G. Honey⁸, C. Bouquet⁸, M. Ly-Le moal⁸, R. Delorme^{4,5,6}, M. Leboyer^{4,7,9}, A. Amestoy^{1,2,3,4}

1 Université de Bordeaux, Bordeaux, France

2 Pôle Universitaire de Psychiatrie de l'Enfant et de l'Adolescent, Hôpital Charles Perrens, Bordeaux, France.

3 Centre national pour la recherche scientifique (INCIA, CNRS UMR 5287), Bordeaux, France

4 Fondation Fondamental, Créteil, France

5 APHP, Robert Debré Hospital, Child and Adolescent Psychiatry Department, Paris, France

6 Pasteur Institute, Paris, France

7 Hôpitaux Universitaires Mondor, CHU PePSY, Pôle de psychiatrie, Fondation FondaMental, Créteil, France.

8 Roche Pharma Research and Early Development, Roche Innovation Center Basel, F. Hoffmann-La Roche Ltd., Grenzacherstrasse 124, 4070 Basel, Switzerland

9 Faculté de Médecine, Université Paris Est, INSERM U955, IMRB, Equipe 15, Psychiatrie Translationnelle, Créteil, France.

Collaborations et Financement

L'étude, à partir de laquelle a été fait ce travail, a été coordonnée par la fondation FondaMental associée à l'Institut National de la Santé Et de la Recherche Médicale (INSERM) et avec la participation de l'Institut Pasteur, de l'Institut Roche de recherche et de médecine translationnelle, émanation du Laboratoire Roche, et des centres experts Asperger du groupement hospitalier Albert Chenevriér – Henri Mondor à Créteil, du centre hospitalier Robert Debré à Paris et du centre hospitalier Charles Perrens à Bordeaux. Le Pr Marion Leboyer était l'investigateur coordinateur et la responsable pour le centre de Créteil. Le Pr Manuel Bouvard était le responsable pour le centre de Bordeaux. Le Pr Richard Delorme était le responsable pour le centre de Paris. Le Pr Thomas Bourgeron était le responsable scientifique.

Le financement de l'étude provient de la fondation FondaMental, de l'INSERM, de l'Institut Pasteur, de l'Institut Roche de recherche et de médecine translationnelle, émanation du Laboratoire Roche, et d'une subvention publique du programme d'investissement d'avenir de l'Agence Nationale de la Recherche (ANR) enregistrée sous le numéro ANR-11-IDEX-0004-02.

Conflits d'intérêt

Aucune rémunération et aucun avantage obtenu par un laboratoire pharmaceutique

Travail en collaboration avec le Laboratoire Roche sur l'étude à partir de laquelle a été fait ce travail.

Résumé

Introduction : Dans le trouble du spectre de l'autisme (TSA), les comorbidités psychiatriques ont un impact négatif important et nécessitent une attention particulière. Il existe peu d'études à l'heure actuelle concernant l'influence des comorbidités psychiatriques sur le regard chez les personnes ayant un TSA. L'objectif de l'étude était d'explorer la relation entre d'une part les niveaux d'anxiété et de dépression et d'autre part le regard chez les individus avec un TSA. **Méthodes :** 62 participants avec un TSA de la cohorte InFoR autisme ont été intégrés dans l'analyse. Il devait avoir un quotient intellectuel au-dessus de 50 et ne pas avoir de pathologie génétique. Les traductions françaises de la Hamilton Anxiety Rating Scale (HARS) et de la Hamilton Depression Rating Scale (HDRS) ont été réalisées pour chaque sujet. L'anxiété sociale a été estimée avec la version française de la Liebowitz Social Anxiety Scale (LSAS). Les sujets ont de plus réalisé une tâche d'analyse du regard en eye-tracking. Ils avaient à déterminer si la personne sur la photographie regardait vers eux ou sur un côté. Des corrélations et des régressions multi-niveaux ont été utilisées pour étudier les associations entre les variables. **Résultats :** Les analyses n'ont pas révélé de lien entre les caractéristiques du regard (temps passé et nombre de fixations sur les yeux ou la face) et la dépression, l'anxiété ou l'anxiété sociale (représentées par la HDRS, la HARS et la LSAS). **Conclusion :** Les résultats ne permettent pas de conclure à une relation entre les comorbidités psychiatriques et le regard chez les personnes avec un TSA. De nouvelles études incorporant un groupe de sujet avec un TSA ayant un diagnostic de dépression ou de trouble anxieux et un groupe de sujet TSA sans comorbidité devrait être plus adaptées pour conclure à l'impact de l'anxiété et de la dépression sur le regard dans le TSA.

Mots clefs

Trouble du spectre de l'autisme, oculométrie, anxiété, dépression, fixation visuelle, durée de fixation visuelle

Abstract

Introduction: In autism spectrum disorder (ASD), burden of psychiatric comorbidities is important and must require attention. To date, the influence of these comorbidities on gaze in subjects with autism is poorly studied. The purpose of the study was to explore the relationship between anxiety and depression levels in one hand and gaze in the other hand in individuals with ASD. **Methods:** 62 participants with an ASD diagnose were picked up from the autism InFoR cohort. They had to have an intellectual quotient above 50 and do not have any genetic condition. French translations of the Hamilton Anxiety Rating Scale (HARS) and of the Hamilton Depression Rating Scale (HDRS) were realized. Social anxiety was estimate with the French version of the Liebowitz Social Anxiety Scale (LSAS). Participants performed a gaze direction task on eye-tracking. They have to determine if the person represented on the pictures looked at them or on one side. Correlations and multilevel models were used to explore associations. **Results:** The analysis didn't reveal link between characteristics of eye movements (time spent looking to face or to eyes and the number of fixation to face or to eyes) and depression, anxiety and social anxiety (represented respectively by HDRS, HARS and LSAS). **Discussion:** This results don't allow concluding to the relationship of psychiatric comorbidities and gaze in autism. Further studies incorporating a group of participants with a confirmed comorbidity of depression disorder or anxiety disorder and a control group should be more powerful and best suited to conclude to the impact of mood or anxiety disorder on eye movements in ASD.

Key words

Autism spectrum disorder, eye-tracking, anxiety, depression, gaze fixation, gaze fixation time

Introduction

In autism spectrum disorder (ASD), about seven out ten children are diagnosed with another psychiatric condition^[1], Comparable rate have been disclosed in adults^[2]. Mood and anxiety disorders are particularly present with highest estimated prevalence around 50 % for anxiety and 70 % for depression^[3-6]. Burden of psychiatric comorbidities is important and must require attention by clinicians. It is an important cause of pharmacological treatment^[2,7,8] and it is linked with parental stress^[9,10]. Furthermore, some of these comorbidities could lead to suicidal ideation, planning or attempts^[11].

ASD is characterized by atypical patterns of impairments in social communication and interactions co-occurring with restricted and repetitive behaviours^[12]. In social interactions people look at the eyes of other persons during most of their time^[13]. Following another person's gaze can lead to judge this person trustworthy^[14]. These mechanisms are impaired in ASD. Abnormality in eyes contact is considered as a core symptom of autism^[12]. The exploration of eye movements is thus an important element in autism research.

Eye-tracking is the processing of measuring the point of gaze or the motion of eyes. It is used in research in multiples fields like reading research^[15], marketing^[16] and human-computer interaction^[17]. Eye-tracking is a non-invasive well validated technique to investigate gaze movements in various mental health clinical populations^[18,19]. It allows following the eye movements constituted of fixations and saccades that putting together constitute scanpath. Saccadic and pursuit eye movements alterations seem involved in psychiatric disorders as depression, anxiety disorder, bipolar disorder and schizophrenia in adults^[18] and children^[20]. They could be linked cognitive and motor systems and reflect immediate psychopathology^[18]. By example in depression, responses are slow^[21]. For persons with depression again, it appears in eye-tracking more fixations and shorter fixation duration^[22,23]. Socially anxious persons have difficult to don't observe facial expressions and thus have an impaired attentional control^[24]. They have both vigilant and avoidant patterns of attention. They avoid maintaining eye contact and exhibit a high vigilance via hyper-scanning of their environment^[25]. Symptoms of anxiety are positively linked with anti-saccade latencies and anti-correlate with pro-saccade amplitude^[22].

In ASD, eye-tracking literature is plentiful. Eye-tracking method has allowed studies targeting social attention and association with measures of social interaction^[26]. A large part of these studies compare subjects with ASD and subjects with a typical development. Scanpaths of subjects with ASD are less controlled and less efficient^[27]. In a meta-analysis, Chita-Tegmark found that persons with ASD spent less time looking for social stimuli than controls^[26]. They showed atypical face processing strategies, impaired face discrimination, impaired face recognition, reduced

attention to eyes and decreased perceptual binding^[28-30]. Eye-tracking studies revealed that strategy for face recognition of adults is compounded of gaze fixations primary converged to face central features (mouth and eyes) to form a triangular scanpath^[31]. ASD individuals have a different scanpath in face exploration^[32]. They have a lower number of fixation on face and spent less time to look face, in particular face core features, than typical development subjects^[30,32-35].

These findings have been related with cerebral imaging and electro-physiological studies. Amygdala and fusiform gyrus activation is linked with time spent on eyes in ASD^[35]. Amygdala activation is correlated with variation in eye fixation, suggesting a greater emotional response to gaze^[35]. Schultz and colleagues argued important role of fusiform gyrus in perception of facial identity and of amygdala in facial expression processing. In his viewpoint, the deficit in amygdala-fusiform gyrus network is linked to autism^[36]. Surprisingly, previous study found that persons with ASD have a hypo-activation of amygdala when making mental inference from eyes^[37]. The impact of eye fixation on amygdala activation in ASD is not yet clearly demonstrated. It is probably linked with the experimental condition. Electro-physiological and eye-tracking studies have suggested that autism is associated with early and late stage processing impairments of facial expressions of emotion^[28,38].

Few protocols have explored link of eye-tracking with clinical assessment and revealed counter-intuitive results. Considering difference between controls and ASD in looking face, the intuitive inference is that more the level of autistic symptoms is high, fewer subjects with ASD look at faces. Astonishingly, high level in autistic symptoms is not associated with reduced looking to the face^[39,40]. No relationship were found between scores on the social skills level and fixations on a potential social partner in a naturalistic situation^[41]. In addition, we could think that comorbidity of ASD and social anxiety will reinforce the hyper-scanning comportment of eye but saccade amplitude and frequency were not correlated with level of social anxiety^[40].

This results open the question of modification of gaze induced by depression or anxiety in ASD. To date, the influence of psychiatric comorbidities on gaze in subjects with autism is poorly studied. Account a greater emotional response to gaze in ASD suggested by amygdala activation association with time spent on eyes^[35], and the reduced looking time of eyes in depression and social anxiety in typical subject^[22,25], we hypothesize that the recrudescence of anxiety or depression symptoms during a comorbid psychiatric episode increase gaze avoidance in individuals with ASD.

The purpose was to study in ASD the relationship between anxiety and depression levels in one hand and gaze movements in the other hand. We wanted to determine if particular modifications in eye-tracking occurred during a depressive or anxious episode in ASD and if these modifications could help to detect the presence of this comorbidities.

Methods

Participants

This study is a part of the InFoR Autism study, a two years longitudinal cohort study including subjects with ASD and control subjects. Volunteers were recruited in three ASD centres in France (Bordeaux, Créteil, Paris) from March 2013 to February 2016. Inclusion criteria for subjects with ASD were fulling ASD criteria of the "Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders – 5" (DSM-5)^[42], have an intellectual quotient above 50 and do not have any genetic condition. The controls exclusion criteria were had neurological, genetic or psychiatric pathology and had an intellectual quotient under 70. The study was approved by regional ethics review board and was registered in the governmental public record for health study on the number NCT02628808. Written consents were given by subjects or their parents if they were under-age.

This work consists of a preliminary analysis of the InFoR Autism cohort. We focused our analysis on data at inclusion. On an initial group of 121, we picked the 62 participants with ASD who did not have missing data.

Clinical assessment

Both psychiatrists and psychologists realized clinical assessment in each centre. For exploration of autistic symptoms, we used a French translation of the "Social Responsiveness Scale" (SRS)^[42] and a French translation of the "Repetitive Behaviour Scale - Revised" (RBS-R)^[43]. SRS is 65-items rating scale over the previous 6 months completed by relatives. It explores the social communication and the social interaction dimension of ASD. RBS-R is a hetero-evaluation by family of the 43 repetitive behaviours referred in DSM version IV^[44]. RBS-R explores the second dimension of ASD, restricted interests and repetitive behaviours.

Concerning emotional aspects, French translations of the Hamilton Anxiety Rating Scale (HARS)^[45] and of the Hamilton Depression Rating Scale (HDRS)^[46] were realized to estimate respectively level of anxiety and level of depression. Level of social anxiety was estimate with the French version of the Liebowitz Social Anxiety Scale (LSAS)^[47,48]. LSAS assess the range of social interaction and performance situations that individuals with social phobia may fear and or avoid. Its 24 items are divided into two sub-scales that address social interactions (11 items) and performance (13 items) situations.

Eye-tracking recording

InFoR Autism included an eye-tracking session composed of multiple tasks such as oculomotor tasks, social tasks, cyber-ball task and emotion recognition tasks. Assuming previous results^[14,32,33,49] and our experimental hypothesis, we conserved the gaze direction task for the

analysis. It was a face processing eye-tracking task. It consisted to establish whether faces on presented picture have looked towards them (CENTRED) or to the sides (ADVERTED) as it is notable on figure 1. 28 pictures were shown during 3 seconds each and speared by black screen. Answers were imputed with L and S touch on a keyboard. Pictures was grouped in three blocks and participants randomized through the blocks. The all task lasts about five minutes. Images were presented by E-prime software on a Tobii TX300, a reflection infra-red optical tracker.

Pictures pre-processing was realized with Tobii studio. Pictures were parsed in area of interest (AOI). The different AOI was face, mouth, nose, two eyes, right eye and left eye. See Figure 1 for details on AOIs delimitation. We keep for clinical considerations face and eye linked AOI. A fixation filter was applied. We used a velocity threshold identification (I-VT) algorithm with parameters similar to those used in de Urabain and colleagues^[50]. This filter is quite conservative in detecting fixations and reduces fixation times, but enables reliable fixation-saccade differentiation. The fix duration time on AOI in milliseconds and the number of fixation by AOI were kept for analysis.

Figure 1: Gaze direction task and AOI definition

A: Two pictures with adverted or centred condition. B: Delimitation of eye right and eye left AOIs. Two eyes are the sum of eye right and eye left. C: Delimitation of Face AOI.

Data analysis

First, we described participants and eye-tracking measures. For continuous variables we estimated mean (m) and standard deviation (sd) and for dichotomic variables, we realized

percentages (%) and count (n). Eye-tracking measures were considered in their raw form and averaged by subject because further analysis using these two formats.

Next, we sought about link within gaze movements and emotional symptoms. We analysed association between eye-tracking measures and clinical data. In the eye-tracking task, each subject has scanned a set of pictures. This pictures could be the same for different subjects. Pictures were splitted in two conditions, ADVERTED and CENTRED. In each picture, we extracted measures of different AOI. This AOI are the same for the different pictures. Thus, eye-tracking measures are nested by AOI at first, by subjects and pictures next and lastly by condition. For these reasons, we analysed independently each AOI in the two conditions. To deal with the nesting by pictures and by subjects, we used two approaches mentioned in the eye-tracking methodological guide of Holmqvist and colleagues^[51].

The first approach was to average data by subjects. Pictures are thus analysed at set by subjects. To analyse averaged variables, we used Pearson (r) or Spearman (rho) correlation depending the normality of data. Coefficient of determination (R^2) was performed as estimation of size effect.

The second approach was mixed effect modelling keeping data in the raw form. It allows to integrate the strata structure of eye-tracking measures within subjects and within pictures. Mixed effects models solve the problem of non-independence/repeated measures through the inclusion of 'random effects' corresponding to the various groups in the sampling design. For the number of fixation on AOI as dependant variable, we use a generalized linear mixed regression with Poisson link and for the fix time duration, we used an identity link. Clinic data were integrated as fix effect. Structuring data and using linear mixed effects models allowed us avoiding issue of dependence through data. Likelihood-ratio test were computed to judge statistical significant of fixed effects following recommendation of lme4 package authors^[52]. Use of mixed models have already been done in eye-tracking studies in similar ways^[53,54].

Every analysis was performed with the language R version 3.3.2^[55] with help of lme4 package version 1.1-12 for linear mixed effect model^[52] and of cowplot version 0.8.0 and ggplot2 version 2.2.1 for graphics^[56,57]. Significant cut-off was 5%.

Results

Clinical assessment results

Almost all our subjects were male (88.71%, $n = 55$). Subjects ranged in age from 7 to 55 years ($m = 18.47$, $sd = 11.12$). Repetitive and restricted behaviours dimension represented by RBS-R and social interaction and communication dimension evaluated by SRS were at moderate levels (respectively $m = 26.48$, $sd = 21.03$ and $m = 72.92$, $sd = 12.21$). Levels of anxiety ($m = 5.08$, $sd = 6.69$) and depression ($m = 3.24$, $sd = 4.89$) were low. Social anxiety was middle with an averaged LSAS total score of 63.87 ($sd = 31.47$).

Eye-tracking results

Eye-tracking was performed on 84 pictures. We got a total of 9 607 recorded AOI and a total of 23 825 fixations. In Table 1, we have detailed for ADVERTED and CENTRED conditions, for each AOI the fixation duration on the AOI and the number of fixation on AOI for both averaged and raw formatting. For face AOI in ADVERTED condition, we got 62 subjects with a mean of 1383.8 ms ($sd = 550.7$) for averaged fix time on AOI and we got 794 records with a mean of 1447.8 ms ($sd = 758$) for raw fix time on AOI. For face AOI but in CENTRED condition, we got 62 subjects with a mean of 1468.8 ($sd = 548.8$) for averaged fix time on AOI and we got 831 records with a mean of 1521 ($sd = 713.2$) for raw fix time on AOI. There were similar means but reduce variability for averaged formatting of eye-tracking measures compared to raw data. ADVERTED and CENTRED conditions shown close means values.

Table 1: Description of eye-tracking measures

AOI	Variable	<i>adverted</i>			<i>centred</i>		
		N	m	sd	N	m	sd
face	averaged fix time on AOI (ms)	62	1383.8	550.7	62	1468.8	548.8
	raw fix time on AOI (ms)	794	1447.8	758	831	1521	713.2
	averaged number of fixation	62	4.9	1.6	62	5.1	1.6
	raw number of fixation	794	5.1	2.6	831	5.3	2.3
two eyes	averaged fix time on AOI (ms)	62	1123.7	565.7	62	1135.9	604.8
	raw fix time on AOI (ms)	789	1179.8	729.9	801	1193.2	743
	averaged number of fixation	62	3.8	1.6	62	3.8	1.6
	raw number of fixation	789	4	2.3	801	4	2.2
eye left	averaged fix time on AOI (ms)	62	557.6	345.4	62	572.2	365.2
	raw fix time on AOI (ms)	794	580.8	567.2	809	599.3	566.8
	averaged number of fixation	62	1.9	0.9	62	1.9	1
	raw number of fixation	794	2	1.8	809	2	1.6
eye right	averaged fix time on AOI (ms)	62	562.5	363.7	62	562.5	340.8
	raw fix time on AOI (ms)	792	596.6	587.2	809	588.5	555.9
	averaged number of fixation	62	1.9	1	62	1.9	1
	raw number of fixation	792	2	1.8	809	2	1.7

N: sample size for variable, %: percentage, n: number of subject with the characteristic, m: mean, sd: standard deviation, AOI: Area Of Interest, ms: millisecond

We observe in Figure 2 the distributions and the main parameters by AOI and conditions for fix duration time on AOI and number of fixation on AOI. For each AOI, we distinguish a large proportion of absence of look. For gaze direction task there was 2656 AOI measures with empty records (27.65 %). Eye-tracking measures are comparable between ADVERTED and CENTRED conditions. Eye left and eye right matched perfectly. Time of observation and number of fixation for these two AOIs very close. As expected two eyes measures were greater than eye right and eye left, and smaller than face. In deed, each eye is content in two eyes and two eyes is content in face.

Figure 2: Manta ray chart, distribution of Fix duration time on AOI and Time to go to AOI in function of AOIs and of Tasks

ms: milliseconds ; Manta ray chart are constituted of the distribution density curves duplicated on both sides with inside the median and quartiles. Subjects are represented by dark points and means by light grey diamonds. We showed Tukey's fence in dark and 1st, 2nd and 3rd bilateral standard deviations in light grey. A: On this graphic for fix duration time on AOI, we note for both conditions equality of mean and median. Eye left and eye right are less symmetric than other AOI. B: On this graphic for number of fixation by AOI, we observe the density curves smoothed as waves. The waves peaks are the integer number with begin at zero. It is the characteristics of count distribution. Waves are less clear for face and two eyes.

Correlations results

We analysed bivariate associations of anxiety and depression levels with fix time duration and number of fixation by AOI. LSAS, HARS and HDRS represented social anxiety, anxiety and depression levels. Number of fixation and fixation duration time represented gaze movements. To

allow correlation, number of fixation and fixation time duration were averaged by subjects. We did not find any link between anxiety and depression levels and gaze movements. All correlations are represented in Table 2. By example, for two eyes AOI in ADVERTED condition, there was no significant correlation between HARS and fix time duration ($\rho = -0.04$, $p = 0.784$, $R^2 = 0$) or number of fixation ($\rho = -0.01$, $p = 0.965$, $R^2 = 0$). There was no significant correlation between LSAS and fix time duration ($r = -0.06$, $p = 0.627$, $R^2 = 0$) or number of fixation ($r = 0.04$, $p = 0.76$, $R^2 = 0$).

For two eyes AOI in CENTRED condition, there was no significant correlation between HARS and fix time duration ($\rho = -0.03$, $p = 0.792$, $R^2 = 0$) or number of fixation ($\rho = 0.01$, $p = 0.936$, $R^2 = 0$). There was no significant correlation between LSAS and fix time duration ($r = -0.03$, $p = 0.839$, $R^2 = 0$) or number of fixation ($r = 0.12$, $p = 0.333$, $R^2 = 0$).

Table 2: Relation between gaze and emotional symptoms using correlation

N = 62			<i>adverted</i>						<i>centred</i>					
AOI	Eye-tracking	Scale	coef type	coef	statistic	df	p	R ²	coef type	coef	statistic	df	p	R ²
face	fix time on AOI	HARS	rho	-0.03	41076.24		0.791	0	rho	-0.07	42382.64		0.603	0
		HDRS	rho	-0.04	41345.61		0.751	0	rho	-0.05	41579.11		0.717	0.01
		LSAS	r	-0.09	-0.66	60	0.509	0.01	rho	-0.03	40919.2		0.814	0
	number of fixation	HARS	rho	0.04	38180.87		0.766	0	rho	-0.02	40341.9		0.902	0
		HDRS	rho	0.05	37801.2		0.71	0	rho	0.01	39174.66		0.917	0
		LSAS	r	-0.02	-0.16	60	0.87	0	r	0.07	0.51	60	0.614	0
two eyes	fix time on AOI	HARS	rho	-0.04	41119.56		0.784	0	rho	-0.03	41066.42		0.792	0
		HDRS	rho	-0.05	41547.43		0.721	0.01	rho	-0.06	42031.34		0.652	0.01
		LSAS	r	-0.06	-0.49	60	0.627	0	r	-0.03	-0.2	60	0.839	0
	number of fixation	HARS	rho	-0.01	39939.54		0.965	0	rho	0.01	39297.3		0.936	0
		HDRS	rho	0.01	39405.03		0.953	0.01	rho	-0.01	40210.85		0.923	0.01
		LSAS	rho	0.04	38140.33		0.76	0	rho	0.12	34751		0.333	0
eye left	fix time on AOI	HARS	rho	-0.03	40737.89		0.842	0	rho	-0.02	40404.18		0.893	0
		HDRS	rho	-0.08	42713.96		0.559	0.01	rho	-0.07	42448.71		0.594	0.01
		LSAS	rho	-0.07	42457.98		0.593	0	rho	-0.04	41321.26		0.754	0
	number of fixation	HARS	rho	0	39784.25		0.989	0	rho	0.02	39055.82		0.899	0
		HDRS	rho	-0.03	40752.96		0.84	0.01	rho	-0.05	41792.54		0.686	0.01
		LSAS	r	-0.07	-0.53	60	0.596	0	r	0.08	0.63	60	0.528	0.01
eye right	fix time on AOI	HARS	rho	-0.01	40169.02		0.929	0	rho	-0.04	41385.72		0.745	0
		HDRS	rho	0.02	38910.04		0.876	0	rho	0	39773.34		0.99	0.01
		LSAS	rho	-0.04	41310.34		0.756	0.01	r	-0.03	-0.27	60	0.788	0
	number of fixation	HARS	rho	0	39614.52		0.985	0	rho	0.03	38442.55		0.805	0
		HDRS	rho	0.05	37652.55		0.689	0	rho	0.08	36640.52		0.55	0
		LSAS	r	0.02	0.19	60	0.853	0	r	0.04	0.28	60	0.783	0

N: sample size for test, coef type: coefficient type, coef: coefficient (rho for Spearman correlation and r for Pearson correlation), statistic: T ratio for Pearson correlation and S for Spearman correlation, df: degree of freedom for T ratio, p: p value, R²: coefficient of determination

HARS: Hamilton Anxiety Rating Scale, HDRS: Hamilton Depression Rating Scale, LSAS : Liebowitz Social Anxiety Scale

Mixed effect models results

To take into account nested structure by subjects and structure of fix time on AOI and number of fixation on AOI, we fitted mixed effect models. Subjects and pictures were considered as random effects to correct repeated assessment by subject and by picture. Number of fixation and fix time were considered as predicted variable while HARS, HDRS and LSAS were integrated as fixed effects. Thereby we could analyse link between fix time and number of fixation in one hand and HARS, LSAS or HDRS in the other hand. Regressions incorporated the 62 subjects of the study.

We did not find significant results. All our models are presented in Table 3. For two eyes AOI in CENTRED condition, there were no significant associations of fix duration time on AOI with HARS (beta = 1143.16, $p = 0.789$), HDRS (beta = 1144.4, $p = 0.431$) and LSAS (beta = 1142.57, $p = 0.827$). Number of fixation were not linked with HARS (beta = 1.24, $p = 0.573$), HDRS (beta = 1.24, $p = 0.325$) and LSAS (beta = 1.24, $p = 0.875$).

Table 3: Relation between gaze and emotional symptoms using mixed effect modeling

AOI	Prediction	Predictor	<i>adverted</i>					<i>centred</i>				
			beta	AIC	chi ²	df	p	beta	AIC	chi ²	df	p
face	fix time on AOI	none		12380.17					12925.24			
		HARS	1403.29	12382.16	0.009	1	0.924	1478.53	12927.06	0.177	1	0.674
		HDRS	1403.87	12382.01	0.16	1	0.689	1478.82	12926.91	0.331	1	0.565
		LSAS	1403.21	12381.79	0.374	1	0.541	1477.77	12927.11	0.129	1	0.72
	number of fixation	none		3550.31					3636.7			
		HARS	1.53	3552.12	0.188	1	0.664	1.61	3638.35	0.349	1	0.555
HDRS		1.53	3552.22	0.09	1	0.764	1.61	3638.58	0.12	1	0.729	
	LSAS	1.53	3552.31	0.001	1	0.977	1.61	3638.44	0.257	1	0.612	
two eyes	fix time on AOI	none		12209.57					12390.1			
		HARS	1135.38	12211.56	0.006	1	0.937	1143.16	12392.03	0.072	1	0.789
		HDRS	1136.74	12211.26	0.301	1	0.583	1144.4	12391.48	0.62	1	0.431
		LSAS	1135.63	12211.37	0.196	1	0.658	1142.57	12392.05	0.048	1	0.827
	number of fixation	none		3260.85					3279.23			
		HARS	1.24	3262.54	0.308	1	0.579	1.24	3280.92	0.318	1	0.573
HDRS		1.24	3262.03	0.821	1	0.365	1.24	3280.27	0.968	1	0.325	
	LSAS	1.24	3262.58	0.269	1	0.604	1.24	3281.21	0.025	1	0.875	
eye left	fix time on AOI	none		12059.59					12286.69			
		HARS	564.45	12061.59	0.002	1	0.967	582.89	12288.69	0.003	1	0.955
		HDRS	565.02	12061.26	0.331	1	0.565	583.64	12288.19	0.5	1	0.48
		LSAS	564.41	12061.59	0.004	1	0.951	582.85	12288.65	0.042	1	0.839
	number of fixation	none		2733.29					2687.92			
		HARS	0.48	2735.09	0.196	1	0.658	0.48	2689.56	0.36	1	0.549
HDRS		0.48	2734.48	0.807	1	0.369	0.48	2688.81	1.108	1	0.293	
	LSAS	0.48	2735.06	0.228	1	0.633	0.48	2689.87	0.051	1	0.821	

			<i>adverted</i>					<i>centred</i>				
AOI	Prediction	Predictor	beta	AIC	chi ²	df	p	beta	AIC	chi ²	df	p
eye right	fix time on AOI	none		12069.05					12265.31			
		HARS	572.12	12070.96	0.093	1	0.76	562.9	12267.12	0.187	1	0.665
		HDRS	572.61	12071.03	0.024	1	0.877	563.14	12266.89	0.412	1	0.521
		LSAS	572.49	12070.74	0.316	1	0.574	562.46	12267.29	0.018	1	0.893
	number of fixation	none		2689.05					2748.96			
		HARS	0.44	2691.04	0.01	1	0.92	0.49	2750.87	0.091	1	0.763
		HDRS	0.44	2690.99	0.06	1	0.807	0.49	2750.72	0.245	1	0.621
	LSAS	0.44	2691.03	0.016	1	0.9	0.49	2750.78	0.182	1	0.669	

AOI: Area Of Interest, exp(beta): exponential transformation of slope of the variable in regression, AIC: Akaike Information Criterion, chi²: statistic of chi square for likelihood-ratio test, df: degree of freedom for chi², p: p value, HARS: Hamilton Anxiety Rating Scale, HDRS: Hamilton Depression Rating Scale, LSAS : Liebowitz Social Anxiety Scale

Discussion

The study aim was to explore in ASD the relationship between anxiety and depression levels in one hand and gaze movements in the other hand. The analysis didn't reveal associations between studied characteristics of eye movements (time spent looking to face or to eyes and the number of fixation to face or to eyes) and depression (represented by HDRS score), anxiety (represented by HARS score) and social anxiety (represented by LSAS score). We didn't find particular modification in eye-tracking during a depressive or anxious episode in participants with ASD. Our hypothesis of an increment of gaze avoiding for eyes region in case of depressive or anxious comorbidity in ASD is not confirmed.

Some limitations in our study may have hindered us in the search for change in visual movements. One of the more important limitation is the low level of anxiety and depression in our sample. Absence of significant associations could result of poor symptom presence. Further approach based on groups of ASD individuals with or without anxious comorbidity rather than based on level of symptoms could be more efficient to detect association of this comorbidity with gaze avoidance. In addition, the generalization of eye-tracking results in ecologic environment could be disrupted by the static nature of used pictures. However, Falkmer and colleagues shown consistency within visual strategies of individuals through static and interactive facial stimuli^[58]. Another bias in eye-tracking experiments is that the performance deficit may not result of the psychopathology but from lack of motivation, bad cooperation or physical limitation^[21]. From a technical standpoint, definition of eye-tracking AOIs is not consensual and differs among studies^[32]. This variation can impact on results because of a restrictive definition for eyes AOIs.

Considering our analysis, although the number of subject is suitable, it remains humble to conclude to no relationship between gaze and emotional disruption. Using mixed effect modelling, also called hierarchical modelling or multilevel modelling has the important advantage to fit to the nested structure of eye-tracking data. It minimizes the need for data aggregation and thus offers a more statistically powerful approach^[53]. There is no overlook of the data pattern. Mixed effects models have already used in eye-tracking studies^[53,54,59-61]. Only Rauthmann and colleagues^[54] use it in study of personality but we didn't find example in the ASD field. The alternative method to mixed effect modelling to incorporate repeated measures by subject is to use an analysis of variance (ANOVA) or covariance incorporating a correction for repeated measures. This method could correct repetition for one variable but not for two like in our analysis (subjects and pictures). Using a mixed effect ANOVA is the strict equivalent of estimate a mixed effect regression. The disadvantage of ANOVA is the absence of estimation of the direction of association between dependant and independent variables.

Concerning link between eye movements and social anxiety, a precedent study found similar results. Eye-tracking characteristics were not correlated with LSAS^[40]. Absence of effect could be linked to an overlap of social interactions dimension between social anxiety and ASD^[62-64]. In adolescents with social anxiety disorder but no ASD, a positive relation between SRS and latency to first fixation at the eyes was found^[65]. The interpretation of these results is not transposable to subjects with ASD. However, it confirms the overlap of symptoms the possible bias induced. Thus, absence of relation of eye movements and social anxiety could be linked to an absence of a clear social anxiety dimension with score of LSAS in large part explained by the social interaction impairment of ASD. In a modest sized pilot study among adolescent with ASD, fear of negative evaluation was linked with greater gaze duration to social threat cues^[66]. The small number of published study on the relationship between anxiety and depression and eye tracking is possibly a publication bias due to absence of significant correlations.

The results and the limitations don't allow concluding to the relationship of psychiatric comorbidities and gaze in autism. Further studies incorporating a group of subjects with a confirmed comorbidity of depression disorder or anxiety disorder and a group with no comorbidity should be more powerful and best suited to conclude to the impact of mood or anxiety disorder on eye movements in ASD. The best knowledge of eye movements in ASD could bring support to new diagnostic and therapeutic approaches. It could permit developing on-line adaptive multi-modal social interaction therapy based on virtual reality. Eye-tracking, within the virtual reality environment, may help facilitate individualization and adaptation, and possibly acceleration of learning emotional cues^[38]. Progress in eye-tracking could lead to use this technique as a para-clinic instrument in mental illness detection^[67].

Acknowledgements

This work has been co-ordinated by Fondation FondaMental and achieved thanks to the following organisms and establishments: AP-HP, CHU Bordeaux, Hôpital Charles Perrens, Robert Debré et Henri Mondor's CIC. We thank Dr T.Bourgeron for his participation.

References

1. Simonoff E, Pickles A, Charman T, Chandler S, Loucas T, Baird G. Psychiatric disorders in children with autism spectrum disorders: Prevalence, comorbidity, and associated factors in a population-derived sample. *Journal of the American Academy of Child and Adolescent Psychiatry* 2008;47(8):921–9.
2. Houghton R, Ong RC, Bolognani F. Psychiatric comorbidities and use of psychotropic medications in people with autism spectrum disorder in the United States. *Autism Research: Official Journal of the International Society for Autism Research* 2017;10(12):2037–47.
3. Joshi G, Wozniak J, Petty C, Martelon MK, Fried R, Bolfek A, et al. Psychiatric Comorbidity and Functioning in a Clinically Referred Population of Adults with Autism Spectrum Disorders: A Comparative Study. *Journal of Autism and Developmental Disorders* 2013;43(6):1314–25.
4. Lugnegård T, Hallerbäck MU, Gillberg C. Psychiatric comorbidity in young adults with a clinical diagnosis of Asperger syndrome. *Research in Developmental Disabilities* Sep-Oct, 20112011;32(5):1910–7.
5. Muris P, Sterneman P, Merckelbach H, Holdrinet I, Meesters C. Comorbid anxiety symptoms in children with pervasive developmental disorders. *Journal of Anxiety Disorders* Jul-Aug, 19981998;12(4):387–93.
6. Nah Y-H, Brewer N, Young RL, Flower R. Brief Report: Screening Adults with Autism Spectrum Disorder for Anxiety and Depression. *Journal of Autism and Developmental Disorders* 2017;
7. Kirino E. Efficacy and tolerability of pharmacotherapy options for the treatment of irritability in autistic children. *Clinical Medicine Insights Pediatrics* 2014;8:17–30.
8. Aman MG, Lam KSL, Collier-Crespin A. Prevalence and Patterns of Use of Psychoactive Medicines Among Individuals with Autism in the Autism Society of Ohio. *Journal of Autism and Developmental Disorders* 2003;33(5):527–34.
9. Giovagnoli G, Postorino V, Fatta LM, Sanges V, De Peppo L, Vassena L, et al. Behavioral and emotional profile and parental stress in preschool children with autism spectrum disorder. *Research in Developmental Disabilities* Oct-Nov, 20152015;45-46:411–21.
10. Hastings RP. Child behaviour problems and partner mental health as correlates of stress in mothers and fathers of children with autism. *Journal of intellectual disability research: JIDR* 2003 May-Jun2003 May-Jun;47(Pt 4-5):231–7.
11. Cassidy S, Bradley P, Robinson J, Allison C, McHugh M, Baron-Cohen S. Suicidal ideation and suicide plans or attempts in adults with Asperger’s syndrome attending a specialist diagnostic clinic:

A clinical cohort study. *The Lancet Psychiatry* 2014;1(2):142–7.

12. American Psychiatric Association. *Diagnostic and statistical manual of mental disorders: DSM-5*. 5th ed. Washington, D.C: American Psychiatric Association; 2013.

13. Hsiao JH-w, Cottrell G. Two fixations suffice in face recognition. *Psychological Science* 2008;19(10):998–1006.

14. Bayliss AP, Tipper SP. Predictive Gaze Cues and Personality Judgments. *Psychological science* 2006;17(6):514–20.

15. Rayner K. Eye movements in reading and information processing: 20 years of research. *Psychological Bulletin* 1998;124(3):372–422.

16. Wedel M, Pieters R. A review of eye-tracking research in marketing. In: *Review of marketing research*. Emerald Group Publishing Limited; 2008. pages 123–47.

17. Hyönä J, Radach R, Deubel H, editors. *The mind's eye: Cognitive and applied aspects of eye movement research*. Amsterdam ; Boston: North-Holland; 2003.

18. Bittencourt J, Velasques B, Teixeira S, Basile LF, Salles JI, Nardi AE, et al. Saccadic eye movement applications for psychiatric disorders. *Neuropsychiatric Disease and Treatment* 2013;9:1393–409.

19. Trillenberg P, Lencer R, Heide W. Eye movements and psychiatric disease. *Current Opinion in Neurology* 2004;17(1):43–7.

20. Rommelse NNJ, Van der Stigchel S, Sergeant JA. A review on eye movement studies in childhood and adolescent psychiatry. *Brain and Cognition* 2008;68(3):391–414.

21. Iacono WG, Lykken DT. Eye Tracking and Psychopathology: New Procedures Applied to a Sample of Normal Monozygotic Twins. *Archives of General Psychiatry* 1979;36(12):1361–9.

22. Li Y, Xu Y, Xia M, Zhang T, Wang J, Liu X, et al. Eye Movement Indices in the Study of Depressive Disorder. *Shanghai Archives of Psychiatry* 2016;28(6):326–34.

23. Müller N, Baumeister S, Dziobek I, Banaschewski T, Poustka L. Validation of the Movie for the Assessment of Social Cognition in Adolescents with ASD: Fixation Duration and Pupil Dilation as Predictors of Performance. *Journal of Autism and Developmental Disorders* 2016;46(9):2831–44.

24. Wieser MJ, Pauli P, Mühlberger A. Probing the attentional control theory in social anxiety: An emotional saccade task. *Cognitive, Affective, & Behavioral Neuroscience* 2009;9(3):314–22.

25. Chen NTM, Clarke PJF. Gaze-Based Assessments of Vigilance and Avoidance in Social Anxiety: A Review. *Current Psychiatry Reports* 2017;19(9):59.

26. Chita-Tegmark M. Social attention in ASD: A review and meta-analysis of eye-tracking studies. *Research in Developmental Disabilities* 2016;48:79–93.
27. Pelphrey KA, Sasson NJ, Reznick JS, Paul G, Goldman BD, Piven J. Visual scanning of faces in autism. *Journal of Autism and Developmental Disorders* 2002;32(4):249–61.
28. Dawson G, Webb SJ, McPartland J. Understanding the nature of face processing impairment in autism: Insights from behavioral and electrophysiological studies. *Developmental neuropsychology* 2005;27(3):403–24.
29. Rutherford MD, Clements KA, Sekuler AB. Differences in discrimination of eye and mouth displacement in autism spectrum disorders. *Vision Research* 2007;47(15):2099–110.
30. Trepagnier C, Sebrechts MM, Peterson R. Atypical face gaze in autism. *Cyberpsychology & Behavior: The Impact of the Internet, Multimedia and Virtual Reality on Behavior and Society* 2002;5(3):213–7.
31. Yarbus AL. *Eye Movements and Vision*. Boston, MA: Springer US; 1967.
32. Amestoy A, Guillaud E, Bouvard MP, Cazalets J-R. Developmental changes in face visual scanning in autism spectrum disorder as assessed by data-based analysis. *Frontiers in Psychology* 2015;6:989.
33. Spezio ML, Adolphs R, Hurley RSE, Piven J. Abnormal Use of Facial Information in High-Functioning Autism. *Journal of Autism and Developmental Disorders* 2007;37(5):929–39.
34. Cassidy S, Mitchell P, Chapman P, Ropar D. Processing of Spontaneous Emotional Responses in Adolescents and Adults with Autism Spectrum Disorders: Effect of Stimulus Type. *Autism Research: Official Journal of the International Society for Autism Research* 2015;8(5):534–44.
35. Dalton KM, Nacewicz BM, Johnstone T, Schaefer HS, Gernsbacher MA, Goldsmith HH, et al. Gaze fixation and the neural circuitry of face processing in autism. *Nature Neuroscience* 2005;8(4):519–26.
36. Schultz RT. Developmental deficits in social perception in autism: The role of the amygdala and fusiform face area. *International Journal of Developmental Neuroscience* 2005;23(2-3):125–41.
37. Baron-Cohen S, Ring HA, Bullmore ET, Wheelwright S, Ashwin C, Williams SC. The amygdala theory of autism. *Neuroscience and Biobehavioral Reviews* 2000;24(3):355–64.
38. Bekele E, Zheng Z, Swanson A, Crittendon J, Warren Z, Sarkar N. Understanding how adolescents with autism respond to facial expressions in virtual reality environments. *IEEE transactions on visualization and computer graphics* 2013;19(4):711–20.

39. Freeth M, Foulsham T, Kingstone A. What Affects Social Attention? Social Presence, Eye Contact and Autistic Traits. *PLOS ONE* 2013;8(1):e53286.
40. Vabalas A, Freeth M. Brief Report: Patterns of Eye Movements in Face to Face Conversation are Associated with Autistic Traits: Evidence from a Student Sample. *Journal of Autism and Developmental Disorders* 2016;46(1):305–14.
41. Laidlaw KEW, Foulsham T, Kuhn G, Kingstone A. Potential social interactions are important to social attention. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences* 2011;108(14):5548–53.
42. Constantino JN. *Social responsiveness scale*. 2nd ed. Los Angeles, California, USA: Western Psychological Services; 2012.
43. Lam KSL, Aman MG. The Repetitive Behavior Scale-Revised: Independent validation in individuals with autism spectrum disorders. *Journal of Autism and Developmental Disorders* 2007;37(5):855–66.
44. American Psychiatric Association, editor. *Diagnostic and statistical manual of mental disorders: DSM-IV ; includes ICD-9-CM codes effective 1. Oct. 96*. 4. ed., 7. print. Washington, DC: 1998.
45. Hamilton M. The assessment of anxiety states by rating. *The British Journal of Medical Psychology* 1959;32(1):50–5.
46. Hamilton M. A rating scale for depression. *Journal of Neurology, Neurosurgery, and Psychiatry* 1960;23(1):56–62.
47. Liebowitz MR. Social phobia. *Modern Problems of Pharmacopsychiatry* 1987;22:141–73.
48. Yao S, Note I, Fanget F, Albuissou E, Bouvard M, Jalenques I, et al. [Social anxiety in patients with social phobia: validation of the Liebowitz social anxiety scale: the French version]. *L'Encephale* 1999;25(5):429–35.
49. Jemel B, Mottron L, Dawson M. Impaired Face Processing in Autism: Fact or Artifact? *Journal of Autism and Developmental Disorders* 2006;36(1):91–106.
50. Saez de Urabain IR, Johnson MH, Smith TJ. GraFIX: A semiautomatic approach for parsing low- and high-quality eye-tracking data. *Behavior Research Methods* 2015;47(1):53–72.
51. Holmqvist K, Nyström M, Andersson R, Dewhurst R, Jarodzka H, Weijer J van de. *Eye Tracking: A comprehensive guide to methods and measures*. OUP Oxford; 2011.
52. Bates D, Maechler M, Bolker B, Walker S. *Lme4: Linear Mixed-Effects Models using 'Eigen' and S4*. 2016.
53. Barr DJ. Analyzing “visual world” eyetracking data using multilevel logistic regression. *Journal*

of Memory and Language 2008;59(4):457–74.

54. Rauthmann JF, Seubert CT, Sachse P, Furtner MR. Eyes as windows to the soul: Gazing behavior is related to personality. *Journal of Research in Personality* 2012;46(2):147–56.

55. R Core Team. *R: A Language and Environment for Statistical Computing*. Vienna, Austria: R Foundation for Statistical Computing; 2016.

56. Wickham H. *Ggplot2: Elegant graphics for data analysis*. New York: Springer; 2009.

57. Wilke CO. *Cowplot: Streamlined Plot Theme and Plot Annotations for 'ggplot2'*. 2016;

58. Falkmer M, Bjällmark A, Larsson M, Falkmer T. The influences of static and interactive dynamic facial stimuli on visual strategies in persons with Asperger syndrome. *Research in Autism Spectrum Disorders* 2011;5(2):935–40.

59. Cop U, Drieghe D, Duyck W. Eye Movement Patterns in Natural Reading: A Comparison of Monolingual and Bilingual Reading of a Novel. *PLoS ONE* 2015;10(8).

60. Franck J, Millotte S, Posada A, Rizzi L. Abstract knowledge of word order by 19 months: An eye-tracking study. *Applied Psycholinguistics* 2013;34.

61. Valuch C, Pflüger LS, Wallner B, Laeng B, Ansorge U. Using eye tracking to test for individual differences in attention to attractive faces. *Frontiers in Psychology* 2015;6.

62. Cath DC, Ran N, Smit JH, van Balkom AJLM, Comijs HC. Symptom overlap between autism spectrum disorder, generalized social anxiety disorder and obsessive-compulsive disorder in adults: A preliminary case-controlled study. *Psychopathology* 2008;41(2):101–10.

63. White SW, Ollendick TH, Bray BC. College students on the autism spectrum: Prevalence and associated problems. *Autism: The International Journal of Research and Practice* 2011;15(6):683–701.

64. White SW, Oswald D, Ollendick T, Scahill L. Anxiety in children and adolescents with autism spectrum disorders. *Clinical Psychology Review* 2009;29(3):216–29.

65. Kleberg JL, Högström J, Nord M, Bölte S, Serlachius E, Falck-Ytter T. Autistic Traits and Symptoms of Social Anxiety are Differentially Related to Attention to Others' Eyes in Social Anxiety Disorder. *Journal of Autism and Developmental Disorders* 2017;47(12):3814–21.

66. White SW, Maddox BB, Panneton RK. Fear of Negative Evaluation Influences Eye Gaze in Adolescents with Autism Spectrum Disorder: A Pilot Study. *Journal of Autism and Developmental Disorders* 2015;45(11):3446–57.

67. Shic F. *Eye Tracking as a Behavioral Biomarker for Psychiatric Conditions: The Road Ahead*.

4. Conclusion générale

Dans le contexte d'inclusion scolaire, les personnes ayant un TSA sont exposées du fait de leur trouble à de nombreux facteurs de stress telle la victimisation et le harcèlement (Paul, 2015). Ces stress pourraient être l'un des facteurs de l'apparition de comorbidités psychiatriques. En plus de l'handicap et de la souffrance du sujet liés au trouble neurodéveloppemental peut venir se surajouter la souffrance et le handicap lié à la comorbidité psychiatrique. Les sujets avec un TSA sont ainsi exposés à un sur-handicap. Le diagnostic de comorbidités psychiatriques dans le TSA est rendu difficile de part les troubles de la communication sociale (American Psychiatric Association, 2013) et de part l'alexithymie (Magnuson & Constantino, 2011). En outre, un symptôme tel l'évitement visuel est commun au TSA et à l'anxiété sociale. Une meilleure connaissance des symptômes devrait faciliter le diagnostic des comorbidités psychiatriques pour le clinicien. Bien que notre travail ne mette pas en lumière de résultats, une technique comme l'eye-tracking peut apporter de nombreux progrès sur la compréhension de l'expression symptomatique des comorbidités dans le TSA. Une bonne compréhension de la modification des symptômes du TSA ou de l'apparition subtile de nouveaux symptômes pourrait permettre une détection plus rapide et une prise en charge accélérée des comorbidités psychiatriques.

Au-delà de ces avancées possibles, des auteurs évoquent d'autres champs de développement de l'eye-tracking. Un premier champ de développement serait l'utilisation de l'eye-tracking comme d'un outil para-clinique (Shic, 2016). Cette technique pourrait cataloguer, quantifier et caractériser des altérations cognitives présentes dans les différents troubles psychiatriques. Bien que regarder un objet n'est pas forcément lié au fait de se concentrer sur cet objet, des atteintes de l'attention, du traitement visuel, du traitement de l'émotion peuvent être mises en évidence dans des tâches d'eye-tracking. Cette perspective nécessiterait des progrès de la technique actuelle. La nature spatiale des données d'eye-tracking suggère de nouveaux développements intégrant des traitements par réseaux neuronaux. L'eye-tracking pourrait de plus servir dans un but thérapeutique. Ainsi, Bekele a évoqué la possibilité d'utiliser l'eye-tracking comme un outil de suivi et de rétrocontrôle dans des tâches de resocialisation en réalité virtuelle (Bekele et al., 2013). Cette utilisation de suivi et de rétrocontrôle de l'eye-tracking dans le cadre d'une activité thérapeutique pourrait s'étendre au-delà de la réalité virtuelle, dans des activités hospitalières ou écologiques.

Références

- 4ème plan autisme - L'autisme - Secrétariat d'État auprès du Premier ministre chargé des Personnes handicapées. (s. d.). Consulté 22 février 2018, à l'adresse <http://handicap.gouv.fr/focus/l-autisme/4eme-plan-autisme/>
- American Psychiatric Association. (2013). *Diagnostic and statistical manual of mental disorders: DSM-5* (5th ed). Washington, D.C: American Psychiatric Association.
- Bekele, E., Zheng, Z., Swanson, A., Crittendon, J., Warren, Z., & Sarkar, N. (2013). Understanding how adolescents with autism respond to facial expressions in virtual reality environments. *IEEE Transactions on Visualization and Computer Graphics*, 19(4), 711-720. <https://doi.org/10.1109/TVCG.2013.42>
- Bhugra, D. (2005). The Global Prevalence of Schizophrenia. *PLoS Medicine*, 2(5). <https://doi.org/10/cbrtdr>
- Bittencourt, J., Velasques, B., Teixeira, S., Basile, L. F., Salles, J. I., Nardi, A. E., ... Ribeiro, P. (2013). Saccadic eye movement applications for psychiatric disorders. *Neuropsychiatric Disease and Treatment*, 9, 1393-1409. <https://doi.org/10.2147/NDT.S45931>
- Cassidy, S., Bradley, P., Robinson, J., Allison, C., McHugh, M., & Baron-Cohen, S. (2014). Suicidal ideation and suicide plans or attempts in adults with Asperger's syndrome attending a specialist diagnostic clinic: a clinical cohort study. *The Lancet Psychiatry*, 1(2), 142-147. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S2215-0366\(14\)70248-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/S2215-0366(14)70248-2)
- Chita-Tegmark, M. (2016). Social attention in ASD: A review and meta-analysis of eye-tracking studies. *Research in Developmental Disabilities*, 48, 79-93. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ridd.2015.10.011>
- Christensen, D. L., Bilder, D. A., Zahorodny, W., Pettygrove, S., Durkin, M. S., Fitzgerald, R. T., ... Yeargin-Allsopp, M. (2016). Prevalence and Characteristics of Autism Spectrum Disorder Among 4-Year-Old Children in the Autism and Developmental Disabilities Monitoring Network. *Journal of Developmental & Behavioral Pediatrics*, 37(1), 1. <https://doi.org/10/f756w9>
- Dawson, G., Webb, S. J., & McPartland, J. (2005). Understanding the nature of face processing impairment in autism: insights from behavioral and electrophysiological studies.

Developmental neuropsychology, 27(3), 403–424.

Diefendorf, A. R., & Dodge, R. (1908). An experimental study of the ocular reactions of the insane from photographic records. *Brain*, 31(3), 451–489.

Haute Autorité de Santé - « Autisme : poursuivons nos efforts » - Tribune de la présidente de la HAS. (s. d.). Consulté 22 février 2018, à l'adresse https://www.has-sante.fr/portail/jcms/c_2829241/fr/-autisme-poursuivons-nos-efforts-tribune-de-la-presidente-de-la-has

Haute Autorité de Santé, & Agence Nationale de l'évaluation et de la qualité des établissements et services sociaux et médico-sociaux. (2017, décembre). Trouble du spectre de l'autisme : interventions et parcours de vie de l'adulte.

Houghton, R., Ong, R. C., & Bolognani, F. (2017). Psychiatric comorbidities and use of psychotropic medications in people with autism spectrum disorder in the United States. *Autism Research: Official Journal of the International Society for Autism Research*, 10(12), 2037-2047. <https://doi.org/10.1002/aur.1848>

Huey, E. B. (1908). *The psychology and pedagogy of reading*. The Macmillan Company.

Hyönä, J., Radach, R., & Deubel, H. (Éd.). (2003). *The mind's eye: cognitive and applied aspects of eye movement research*. Amsterdam ; Boston: North-Holland.

Joshi, G., Petty, C., Wozniak, J., Henin, A., Fried, R., Galdo, M., ... Biederman, J. (2010). The heavy burden of psychiatric comorbidity in youth with autism spectrum disorders: a large comparative study of a psychiatrically referred population. *Journal of Autism and Developmental Disorders*, 40(11), 1361-1370. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10803-010-0996-9>

Joshi, G., Wozniak, J., Petty, C., Martelon, M. K., Fried, R., Bolfek, A., ... Biederman, J. (2013). Psychiatric comorbidity and functioning in a clinically referred population of adults with autism spectrum disorders: a comparative study. *Journal of Autism and Developmental Disorders*, 43(6), 1314-1325. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10803-012-1679-5>

Kirino, E. (2014). Efficacy and tolerability of pharmacotherapy options for the treatment of irritability in autistic children. *Clinical Medicine Insights. Pediatrics*, 8, 17-30. <https://doi.org/10.4137/CMPed.S8304>

Lugnegård, T., Hallerbäck, M. U., & Gillberg, C. (2011). Psychiatric comorbidity in young adults with a clinical diagnosis of Asperger syndrome. *Research in Developmental Disabilities*,

32(5), 1910-1917. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ridd.2011.03.025>

Magnuson, K. M., & Constantino, J. N. (2011). Characterization of Depression in Children with Autism Spectrum Disorders. *Journal of developmental and behavioral pediatrics : JDBP*, 32(4), 332-340. <https://doi.org/10.1097/DBP.0b013e318213f56c>

Muris, P., Steerneman, P., Merckelbach, H., Holdrinet, I., & Meesters, C. (1998). Comorbid anxiety symptoms in children with pervasive developmental disorders. *Journal of Anxiety Disorders*, 12(4), 387-393.

Nah, Y.-H., Brewer, N., Young, R. L., & Flower, R. (2017). Brief Report: Screening Adults with Autism Spectrum Disorder for Anxiety and Depression. *Journal of Autism and Developmental Disorders*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10803-017-3427-3>

Paul, A. (2015, septembre 17). *Phénomènes de victimisation chez les enfants et adolescents avec trouble du spectre de l'autisme*. Université de Bordeaux, Bordeaux. Consulté à l'adresse <https://dumas.ccsd.cnrs.fr/dumas-01208258/document>

Rayner, K. (1998). Eye movements in reading and information processing: 20 years of research. *Psychological Bulletin*, 124(3), 372-422. <https://doi.org/10/b5gdrv6>

Rommelse, N. N. J., Van der Stigchel, S., & Sergeant, J. A. (2008). A review on eye movement studies in childhood and adolescent psychiatry. *Brain and Cognition*, 68(3), 391-414. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bandc.2008.08.025>

Rutherford, M. D., Clements, K. A., & Sekuler, A. B. (2007). Differences in discrimination of eye and mouth displacement in autism spectrum disorders. *Vision Research*, 47(15), 2099-2110. <https://doi.org/10/cbm8h6>

Shic, F. (2016). Eye Tracking as a Behavioral Biomarker for Psychiatric Conditions: The Road Ahead. *Journal of the American Academy of Child and Adolescent Psychiatry*, 55(4), 267-268. <https://doi.org/10/gcx445>

Simonoff, E., Pickles, A., Charman, T., Chandler, S., Loucas, T., & Baird, G. (2008). Psychiatric disorders in children with autism spectrum disorders: prevalence, comorbidity, and associated factors in a population-derived sample. *Journal of the American Academy of Child and Adolescent Psychiatry*, 47(8), 921-929. <https://doi.org/10.1097/CHI.0b013e318179964f>

The NHS Information Centre, Community and Mental Health Team, Brugha, T., Cooper, S.,

McManus, S., Purdon, S., Smith, J., ... Tyrer, F. (2012). *Estimating the Prevalence of Autism Spectrum Conditions in Adults - Extending the 2007 Adult Psychiatric Morbidity Survey*. The NHS Information Centre. Consulté à l'adresse <https://digital.nhs.uk/catalogue/PUB05061>

Wedel, M., & Pieters, R. (2008). A review of eye-tracking research in marketing. In *Review of marketing research* (p. 123–147). Emerald Group Publishing Limited.

Index des Tableaux

Table 1: Description of eye-tracking measures.....	21
Table 2: Relation between gaze and emotional symptoms using correlation.....	24
Table 3: Relation between gaze and emotional symptoms using mixed effect modeling.....	26

Index des Figures

Figure a : Représentation de l'obtention du vecteur entre le centre de la pupille et la réflexion cornéenne permettant de calculer la rotation de l'œil.....	9
Figure 1: Gaze direction task and AOI definition.....	18
Figure 2: Manta ray chart, distribution of Fix duration time on AOI and Time to go to AOI in function of AOIs and of Tasks.....	22

Résumé :

Introduction : Dans le trouble du spectre de l'autisme (TSA), les comorbidités psychiatriques ont un impact négatif important et nécessitent une attention particulière. Il existe peu d'études à l'heure actuelle concernant l'influence des comorbidités psychiatriques sur le regard chez les personnes ayant un TSA. L'objectif de l'étude était d'explorer la relation entre d'une part les niveaux d'anxiété et de dépression et d'autre part le regard chez les individus avec un TSA. **Méthodes :** 62 participants avec un TSA de la cohorte InFoR autisme ont été intégrés dans l'analyse. Il devait avoir un quotient intellectuel au-dessus de 50 et ne pas avoir de pathologie génétique. Les traductions françaises de la Hamilton Anxiety Rating Scale (HARS) et de la Hamilton Depression Rating Scale (HDRS) ont été réalisées pour chaque sujet. L'anxiété sociale a été estimée avec la version française de la Liebowitz Social Anxiety Scale (LSAS). Les sujets ont de plus réalisé une tâche d'analyse du regard en eye-tracking. Ils avaient à déterminer si la personne sur la photographie regardait vers eux ou sur un côté. Des corrélations et des régressions multi-niveaux ont été utilisées pour étudier les associations entre les variables. **Résultats :** Les analyses n'ont pas révélé de lien entre les caractéristiques du regard (temps passé et nombre de fixations sur les yeux ou la face) et la dépression, l'anxiété ou l'anxiété sociale (représentées par la HDRS, la HARS et la LSAS). **Conclusion :** Les résultats ne permettent pas de conclure à une relation entre les comorbidités psychiatriques et le regard chez les personnes avec un TSA. De nouvelles études incorporant un groupe de sujet avec un TSA ayant un diagnostic de dépression ou de trouble anxieux et un groupe de sujet TSA sans comorbidité devrait être plus adaptées pour conclure à l'impact de l'anxiété et de la dépression sur le regard dans le TSA.

Mots clefs :

Trouble du spectre de l'autisme, oculométrie, anxiété, dépression, fixation visuelle, durée de fixation visuelle

Abstract:

Introduction: In autism spectrum disorder (ASD), burden of psychiatric comorbidities is important and must require attention. To date, the influence of these comorbidities on gaze in subjects with autism is poorly studied. The purpose of the study was to explore the relationship between anxiety and depression levels in one hand and gaze in the other hand in individuals with ASD. **Methods:** 62 participants with an ASD diagnose were picked up from the autism InFoR cohort. They had to have an intellectual quotient above 50 and do not have any genetic condition. French translations of the Hamilton Anxiety Rating Scale (HARS) and of the Hamilton Depression Rating Scale (HDRS) were realized. Social anxiety was estimate with the French version of the Liebowitz Social Anxiety Scale (LSAS). Participants performed a gaze direction task on eye-tracking. They have to determine if the person represented on the pictures looked at them or on one side. Correlations and multilevel models were used to explore associations. **Results:** The analysis didn't reveal link between characteristics of eye movements (time spent looking to face or to eyes and the number of fixation to face or to eyes) and depression, anxiety and social anxiety (represented respectively by HDRS, HARS and LSAS). **Discussion:** This results don't allow concluding to the relationship of psychiatric comorbidities and gaze in autism. Further studies incorporating a group of participants with a confirmed comorbidity of depression disorder or anxiety disorder and a control group should be more powerful and best suited to conclude to the impact of mood or anxiety disorder on eye movements in ASD.

Key words:

Autism spectrum disorder, eye-tracking, anxiety, depression, gaze fixation, gaze fixation time

Travail effectué au Centre Ressources Autisme Aquitaine

Pôle universitaire de psychiatrie de l'enfant et de l'adolescent, Chef de pôle : Pr Manuel Bouvard

Responsable : Dr Anouck Amestoy, Centre Hospitalier Charles Perrens

121 rue de la Béchade - CS 81285, 33076 Bordeaux Cedex

François A.M. Jean

Anxiété, Dépression et Regard dans le TSA : Étude en Oculométrie

Mémoire DESC de Pédoopsychiatrie - Année 2018